

ENHANCING RURAL AESTHETICS: REVIVING RESIDENTIAL CULTURE IN BEAUTIFUL COUNTRYSIDE CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract

Residential culture, deeply rooted in traditional Chinese heritage, plays a pivotal role in the development of beautiful rural areas. By preserving and revitalizing residential culture, rural regions can enhance their cultural depth, historical significance, and overall appeal. This paper employs the wooden structure architecture of the Dong ethnic group as a case study to explore the practical implications and feasibility of leveraging residential culture to advance the creation of beautiful rural areas. The findings of this research aim to provide valuable insights and recommendations for the enhancement and sustainable development of rural communities, contributing to their prosperity and cultural preservation.

1. Introduction

In the construction of beautiful rural areas, residential culture is an indispensable and important content. Residential culture is an important component of traditional Chinese culture and an important heritage of China's historical and cultural heritage. By excavating and inheriting residential culture, the cultural connotations and historical heritage of rural areas can be enriched, and the attractiveness and competitiveness of rural areas can be improved. Therefore, utilizing residential culture to promote the construction of beautiful rural areas is of great significance and value. This article takes the wooden structure architecture of the Dong ethnic group as an example to explore the feasibility and practical significance of promoting the construction of beautiful rural areas through the use of residential culture^[1]. Through the research in this article, we hope to provide useful ideas and references for promoting the construction of beautiful rural areas, and make positive contributions to the development and construction of rural areas^[2].

2. The role of residential culture in the construction of beautiful countryside

2.1 Enriching the cultural connotations and historical heritage of rural areas

Residential culture is an important cultural resource in rural areas. By exploring and inheriting residential culture, it can enrich the cultural connotations and historical heritage of rural areas. Residential culture is an important component of traditional culture, containing rich cultural connotations and historical information. By studying

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and inheriting residential culture, people can understand and understand traditional culture, improve cultural literacy and self-confidence, and provide strong support for researching and protecting traditional culture.

2.2 Enhancing the attractiveness and competitiveness of rural areas

Residential culture is an important cultural resource in rural areas, and by exploring and inheriting it, it can enhance the attractiveness and competitiveness of rural areas. Residential culture is an important cultural symbol in rural areas, with significant cultural and historical value. By protecting and inheriting residential culture, the visibility and reputation of rural areas can be improved, in order to attract more tourists and investors to rural areas, and promote their development and prosperity^[3].

2.3 Promoting the implementation of beautiful rural construction

The construction of beautiful rural areas aims to build a beautiful natural environment, livable living environment, and rich cultural environment, improve the ecological environment and living conditions in rural areas, and promote economic and social development in rural areas. In the construction of beautiful rural areas, exploring and inheriting residential culture can provide beneficial support and guarantee for the construction of beautiful rural areas. By protecting and inheriting residential culture, we can fully utilize the cultural resources of rural areas, enhance their cultural connotations and historical heritage, and provide distinctive and charming cultural resources for the construction of beautiful rural areas.

2.4 Promoting community cohesion and social harmony

The inheritance and development of residential culture can promote community cohesion and social harmony. As a place for people to live, residential buildings carry the emotions and memories of community residents. By excavating and inheriting residential culture, community residents can enhance their sense of belonging and identity, and promote harmony in neighborhood relationships. At the same time, the inheritance of residential culture can also stimulate the enthusiasm of community residents to participate and promote the common development and progress of the community.

3. The characteristics of Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture

The Dong ethnic group is an ethnic group in southern China, distributed in Guizhou, Hunan, Guangxi, and other places. The traditional architecture of the Dong ethnic group is a wooden structure architecture, which has unique characteristics and reflects the cultural and historical background of the Dong ethnic group. Its architectural characteristics are as follows:

3.1 The building structure is simple and stable

The plane shape of buildings is generally triangular and quadrilateral, while the roof adopts a broken line or ladder shape. This architectural form can provide good stability and enable the building to withstand the impact of natural disasters. At the same time, mortise tenon structure and arch of wooden architecture structure are often used in the structure of traditional buildings of the Dong ethnic group, which can withstand horizontal and vertical forces and have good seismic and wind resistance. In the mortise and tenon structure, the precise processing of the mortise and tenon makes the structure more compact and firmer, while also avoiding the use of metal connectors such as nails and screws to damage the wood. Arch of wooden architecture structure uses bucket shaped stone piers or wooden columns to support the arch structure, making the weight of the building more evenly distributed, thus enhancing the stability and seismic resistance of the building^[4]. The application of this structural form not only reflects the superb skills of the Dong ethnic group's wooden structure architecture, but also reflects the wisdom and creativity of the Dong ethnic group.

3.2 Selection of natural and environmentally friendly building materials

The building materials for Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings are natural and environmentally friendly, not only because these materials have good environmental and ecological properties, but also because they are more in line with local climate and environmental requirements, with better adaptability and plasticity. The wood used in Dong ethnic wooden structures is mostly local natural materials, such as pine, fir, teak, etc.^[5]. These woods have the characteristics of toughness, durability, fine texture, and easy processing, and are widely used in the construction and decoration of Dong ethnic wooden structures. In traditional Dong architecture, bamboo is often used as a covering material for roofs. Through special weaving techniques, various beautiful roof shapes and patterns are formed, making the roofs more beautiful and practical. Soil and stone are usually used for the construction of foundations and walls because they can provide stable support and protection. Soil and stone are commonly used building materials in Dong architecture, which not only have good stability and insulation performance, but also have good ecological and environmental protection. In Dong ethnic wooden structures, soil and stone are widely used in the foundation and wall parts of buildings to provide better support and protection. Earth wall is a common architectural form in Dong ethnic wooden structures. It not only has good sound insulation, thermal insulation, and fire resistance performance, but also effectively prevents weathering and water erosion, making it a very practical architectural form.

3.3 The architectural form is simple and full of changes

Traditional Dong architecture usually adopts a single-story or multi-story bungalow structure, with a broken line or ladder shaped roof. In addition to the bungalow style structure, there are also many special architectural forms, such as water buildings, wind and rain bridges, drum towers, and towers. Water architecture is a form of architecture used by the Dong ethnic group when living in a water town area. Its architectural structure and appearance have strong water town characteristics, such as "Wind and Rain Bridge Building", "Water Car House", "Peach Blossom Fortress", etc. Fengyu Bridge is a special architectural form formed by the Dong people in their long-term production and life. It is commonly found in mountainous and valley areas and not only has practical functions, but also an important component of Dong culture. Drum towers and towers are important forms of traditional architecture of the Dong ethnic group. They not only have practical functions, but also serve as important expressions of Dong culture and art, commonly found in Dong inhabited areas and religious places. These special architectural forms have high artistic and cultural value in traditional Dong architecture, showcasing the unique charm of Dong architecture through clever design and exquisite craftsmanship.

3.4 Architectural decoration is rich in ethnic characteristics

Decoration usually adopts traditional techniques such as carving, color painting, and lacquer painting, with distinct patterns and colors, and rich ethnic characteristics. Auspicious patterns and ethnic customs, such as fish, flowers, birds, insects, dragons, etc., are often painted on the exterior walls and doors of buildings. These patterns represent the cultural traditions and beliefs of the Dong people, and also reflect their reverence for nature and life. The tiles on the roof and the wood carvings under the eaves are also one of the characteristics of Dong architecture. These carvings are meticulous and unique, often representing the life and culture of the Dong people, and are also important manifestations of Dong culture and art. These decorations not only have high artistic value, but also are an important component of Dong culture and history, and are important symbols and symbols of Dong culture. Through these decorations, the Dong people have inherited and promoted their own culture, while also adding unique artistic charm to the architecture.

3.5 Having regional and cultural heritage characteristics

Dong architecture is designed and constructed based on the local natural and cultural environment, as well as the cultural traditions of the Dong ethnic group, thus possessing distinct regional characteristics. The construction of Dong ethnic wooden structures requires the selection of local natural materials, such as wood, stone, bamboo, etc. Through clever structural design and exquisite architectural techniques, these materials can be transformed into beautiful, practical, and durable buildings to adapt to the local climate and living environment. Therefore, Dong wooden structure buildings not only have practical value, but also reflect the local culture, history, and cultural environment, making them one of the important carriers of Dong culture. By inheriting and developing Dong wooden structure architecture, it can promote the inheritance and development of Dong culture, protect and promote Dong's cultural heritage. Inheriting Dong wooden structure architecture not only means protecting an important component of Dong culture, but also a way to inherit and promote Dong traditional culture.

4. The application of Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture in the construction of beautiful countryside

4.1 Protection and restoration of traditional wooden structure buildings

Traditional wooden structure buildings, as an important component of Dong ethnic rural cultural heritage, carry rich historical and cultural connotations. Therefore, protecting and repairing these buildings is crucial for achieving the goal of building beautiful rural areas. Firstly, protecting traditional wooden structures helps to preserve the historical memory of rural areas and pass on the cultural traditions passed down from generation to generation. The historical stories and cultural symbols carried by these buildings allow people to feel the wisdom and lifestyle of the Dong people. Secondly, repairing wooden structures can showcase the unique architectural style and traditional craftsmanship of the Dong ethnic group. By restoring and restoring the original appearance of buildings, rural areas can showcase their unique ethnic and cultural characteristics, attracting the attention of tourists and researchers. The restored wooden structures have become a landmark landscape in rural areas, adding a strong cultural atmosphere to the countryside. At the same time, the protection and restoration of wooden structures are also the inheritance and promotion of traditional craftsmanship. The woodworking techniques and decorative details used in these buildings showcase the craftsmanship skills passed down from generation to generation by the Dong people. By repairing wooden structures, the inheritance and development of these traditional crafts can be promoted. In the process of protecting and restoring traditional wooden structure buildings, it is necessary to pay attention to the balance between inheritance and innovation, not only preserving the original style and characteristics of the building, but also combining modern building technology and materials for moderate transformation and restoration. By comprehensively considering the historical value, cultural significance, and functional needs of the building, the repaired wooden structure building can play a greater role in the construction of beautiful rural areas, becoming a unique cultural landscape and attraction in rural areas. At the same time, this also provides new opportunities for the economic development of rural areas. For example, through the restoration and utilization of wooden structures, related industries such as cultural tourism and homestay management can be carried out, promoting the diversified development of rural economy. In summary, protecting and restoring traditional wooden structure buildings is of great significance in the construction of beautiful rural areas. It can not only preserve the historical memory and cultural traditions of the countryside, but also showcase the unique architectural style and traditional craftsmanship of the Dong ethnic group.

4.2 Promoting rural landscape improvement through the use of wooden structure buildings

Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture, with its unique form and aesthetic characteristics, provides unique elements and style for rural landscapes. In the construction of beautiful rural areas, reasonable layout and design

of wooden structure buildings are crucial. By fully considering the characteristics of the natural environment and surrounding landscapes, and coordinating wooden structures with them, we can create rural landscapes with regional characteristics and strong cultural connotations. The layout and design of Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings emphasize the integration with the natural environment, making them more harmonious in rural landscapes. The form of the building, the shape of the roof, and the carving of the facade all showcase the unique charm of Dong architecture. The natural materials and traditional craftsmanship of wooden structures complement the surrounding natural environment, blend with mountains and rivers, and blend with rural areas, forming a beautiful rural painting. The uniqueness of wooden architecture lies not only in its appearance, but also in the design of its internal space. The layout and functional settings of the internal space fully consider the living habits and cultural traditions of the Dong people. For example, the reasonable division of the living room and kitchen, as well as the connection between the living room and bedroom, all reflect the lifestyle and values of the Dong people. This reasonable spatial planning not only provides a comfortable living environment, but also provides a platform for rural residents to showcase their own culture and lifestyle.

Through reasonable layout and design, Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings are integrated with the natural environment, forming a unique landscape style. These buildings, with their exquisite woodworking skills and unique decorative details, present a strong ethnic cultural characteristic. Whether it is the carved patterns on the eaves and corners of the roof, the window lattice, or the painted decoration on the exterior of the building, all demonstrate the essence of traditional Dong craftsmanship. These details and decorations not only beautify the building itself, but also add a unique artistic atmosphere and cultural connotation to the rural landscape.

4.3 The integration of wood structure architecture and rural industrial development

The application of Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings not only enhances the cultural value of rural areas, but also injects new vitality into the development of rural industries. Combining wooden structures with industries such as rural tourism, homestays, and handicrafts can promote the diversified development of rural economy, provide more employment opportunities for rural residents, and improve their quality of life. The rural tourism industry based on wooden structure buildings has enormous development potential. These buildings, as representatives of cultural heritage, attract tourists to explore and experience Dong culture. Tourists can appreciate the unique aesthetic charm of wooden structures and learn about the architectural traditions and ethnic culture of the Dong ethnic group. At the same time, the restoration and utilization of wooden structures also provide rich tourism resources and attractions for rural areas, attracting more tourists to visit and experience. With the development of rural tourism, the surrounding industries such as catering, specialties, and handicrafts will also be improved, thereby driving the prosperity of the rural economy.

In addition, the rural homestay industry based on wooden structures has gradually emerged. The restored wooden structure building, with its unique style and comfortable living environment, attracts tourists who pursue authenticity and return to nature. The rural homestay industry provides a close accommodation experience to nature, allowing tourists to deeply experience the tranquility and beauty of the countryside. The development of rural homestays not only creates economic income for rural residents, but also promotes the sales of local agricultural products and the promotion of rural specialty handicrafts. The combination of wooden structure architecture and rural handicraft industry has also injected new vitality into the rural economy. The restoration and protection of wooden structures of the Dong ethnic group require a lot of woodworking skills and traditional craftsmanship skills. This has prompted local craftsmen and carpenters to inherit and promote the traditional craftsmanship of the Dong ethnic group, providing professional technical support for the restoration of wooden structures.

4.4 Cultural symbols and ethnic identity

Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture, as an important symbol of national culture, plays an irreplaceable role in the construction of beautiful rural areas. These buildings are not only a form of residence, but also a symbol of the Dong people's love and identification with their homes and traditional culture. They integrate rich history, religion, lifestyle, and aesthetic concepts, carrying the deep emotions of the Dong people towards land, nature, and life. In the construction of beautiful rural areas, the protection and display of Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings as cultural symbols can stimulate rural residents' sense of pride and identification with their own culture. By repairing and protecting these buildings, we showcased the unique charm of traditional Dong architecture to rural residents and tourists, and promoted the deep affection and kindness of the Dong people towards their homes. At the same time, protecting wooden structure buildings is also an important support for the cultural tradition of the Dong ethnic group. They are the crystallization of wisdom and skills from generation to generation, representing the history and spirit of rural areas.

By strengthening the inheritance and cultivation of traditional architectural techniques in Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture, we can promote the traditional inheritance and innovative development of Dong ethnic culture. Traditional woodworking techniques have been inherited and promoted in the process of repairing wooden structures, providing the younger generation with the opportunity to learn and inherit these valuable crafts. Through the inheritance and innovation of traditional craftsmanship, we can infuse the spiritual connotation of Dong ethnic wooden structure architecture into modern design, creating a more contemporary architectural form that meets contemporary needs. Such efforts can not only enhance the practicality and functionality of wooden structures, but also promote the traditional development of Dong culture, giving it new vitality.

4.5 Ecological environmental protection and sustainable development

As a building form mainly using natural wood, Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings exhibit excellent ecological and environmental protection performance and sustainable development characteristics. It is based on the effective utilization of wood resources, reducing environmental damage and resource waste. In the construction of beautiful rural areas, promoting the use of wooden structure buildings is a major measure to promote the development of green buildings. The use of wooden structures can effectively reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions, thereby reducing the negative impact of buildings on the environment. Compared to traditional concrete and steel structures, wooden structures have lower energy consumption and carbon footprint. Through the large-scale application of wooden structure buildings, we can achieve green and sustainable goals in rural construction, protect the ecological environment, and leave a better rural heritage for future generations.

5. Conclusion

Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings, as an important component of rural cultural heritage, play an irreplaceable role in the construction of beautiful rural areas. Through the protection, restoration, and application of Dong ethnic wooden structure buildings, cultural inheritance, improvement of rural landscapes, development of rural industries, and protection of the ecological environment can be achieved in rural areas. This is not only the cherishing and inheritance of Dong culture, but also a unique exploration and practice of rural development.

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